

114°E

120°E

126°E

132°E

138°E

144°E

150°E

156°E

12°S

12°S

16°S

16°S

20°S

20°S

24°S

24°S

28°S

28°S

32°S

32°S

36°S

36°S

40°S

40°S

44°S

44°S

114°E

120°E

126°E

132°E

138°E

144°E

150°E

156°E

*INDIAN
OCEAN*

Coral Sea

**NORTHERN
TERRITORY**

QUEENSLAND

**WESTERN
AUSTRALIA**

**SOUTH
AUSTRALIA**

**NEW SOUTH
WALES**

Great Australian Bight

A. C. T.

VICTORIA

Tasman Sea

0 500 1000 km

TASMANIA